

Event Series Completion as a Prerequisite Towards a Gold Standard Scientific Event Corpus

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Abstract. Scientific activities based on interaction in the social network manifested by scientific meetings revolve around authors, papers, proceedings, events and event series. The links and traces between these core entities form the conceptual scientific knowledge graph. Commercial and non-commercial players implement this conceptual graph as an interlinked network of scientific knowledge graphs by supplying infrastructure, metadata and software. Metadata about scientific events and event series are key connecting parts of these graphs. Scholars need to easily navigate these graphs – be it in hypertext form as links or via queries. FAIR Navigability without obstacles is a prerequisite for use cases such as bibliographic reference management or the organization of future events. Digital bi-directional traceability from any node in the conceptual knowledge graph to any other is not possible if the quality of metadata about events and event series is so low that in effect the necessary links are missing, broken or otherwise being obstacles. References to events and event series are the base source of these links in the conceptual scientific knowledge graph. However, most of these references are still majorly kept as natural language bibliographic references and therefore are ambiguous and error prone. While there are already persistent identifiers (PIDs) for papers, people and organizations to clearly identify the corresponding link target and point to a corresponding corpus or infrastructure, there is no such solution for de-referencing PIDs based on an event corpus for scientific events. Even if an event may be identified and metadata be found in one of the data sources, the crucial metadata that links the event to its event series and thus to the history of the event series is too often incomplete or missing. This mostly empirical work presents a scientific event corpus covering more than 10 different sources and proposes necessary and viable steps to make event series completion possible as a prerequisite towards a gold standard scientific event corpus.

Keywords: Metadata · Scientific Events · Scholarly Knowledge Graph · Gold Standard · Corpus

1 Introduction

Metadata corpora about scientific events are the basis for a broad range of use cases, including support for decision making regarding the submission, event participation, and taking organizational roles [18]. Helping to recognize fraudulent conferences is an important step in this decision making process. In prior work, we have stated this problem, identified use cases, and pointed out the need for assigning Persistent Identifiers (PID) to conferences [18]; see also section 2.2.

The current state of scientific event corpora is not satisfactory since the digitization and support for bidirectional traceability of artefacts on the process and implementation level suffers from too many data quality issues. Versi states that a gold standard is the best available yardstick [64] to test a scientific proposition. Over time, a better standard may replace it, but in the area of scientific event corpora, there is not even an initial gold standard yet which would at least meet basic FAIR [71] criteria.

Questions such as “What conferences did members of our research department publish papers for in the last 10 years?” should be answerable by a gold standard scientific event corpus with a simple query that makes the results available in computer readable form for further analysis. As of the publication of this work such a gold standard does

not exist yet, since the data quality is not sufficient and the event series information is incomplete or missing in most of the cases.

Table 1 relates common issues of scientific event metadata to those ISO 25012 [32] data quality criteria that are in the focus of this work. Further quality criteria, such as efficiency, traceability or understandability are also applied.

Table 1. Common data quality issues of scientific event metadata

# Issue	ISO 25012 criteria
1 Events are missing – event series are incomplete	completeness, currentness
2 Metadata is missing – the key metadata of events is incomplete	completeness
3 Metadata is wrong	accuracy, consistency
4 Metadata is not computer readable/queryable	portability, availability, accessibility
5 Metadata of potentially predatory events is mixed with that of trust-worthy ones	credibility

Consider the example of the event series ACCV – Asian Conference on Computer Vision – which has been organized by the Asian Federation of Computer Vision Societies since 1993 [1]. WikiCFP for instance ⁴ shows entries for the 16th (2022), 14th (2018) and 11th (2012) installment and a 2020 event that has no such ordinal/enumeration information. Common sense leads to the conclusion that ACCV is a biannual event and the first event might have been in 1992 and the 2020 event was the 15th. ⁵ ACCV 2021⁶ is an event whose acronym suggests that it might be part of the well known and reputable ACCV. However, in fact it is not part of that conference series. Given the attempt to make use of the acronym of another conference, this ACCV 2021 is a candidate for being checked whether it is predatory.

The manually curated OpenResearch.org [44] event wiki even contained an entry for this “cuckoo’s egg” event until semi-automated checks, which are part of our work, found the quality issue. At the time of writing, none of the sources inspected covered all 16 events of this series. The crucial ordinal information (1st, 2nd, . . . , 16th) that is needed for such semi-automated checks was not computer readable in the raw data of most sources. The ACCV example exposes all the issues mentioned above for just one event series. We analyze how common such problems are in general and propose remedies towards a gold standard. The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 introduces the core concepts required for discussing scientific events and also reviews relevant related work. Section 3 explains how the ConferenceCorpus was created and implemented. Section 4 shows key findings regarding the event signature availability, the ordinal distribution and the completeness of event series as well as limitations. Section 5 covers the conclusion and future work.

2 Background and Related Work

Completeness of event series metadata is of crucial importance for the use case of decision support. The poll at PIDapalooza 2020 [57] supports this need as the top answer for “Which quality criteria define a high quality event for you?” was “Event

⁴ <http://www.wikicfp.com/cfp/program?id=22>

⁵ Our research shows that quite a few conference series’ frequency and naming schemes do not follow common sense approaches

⁶ <http://www.wikicfp.com/cfp/servlet/event.showcfp?eventid=113719>

is part of a well established series”. Systematically determining whether an event is part of a well established series calls for the availability of metadata on both the event and the corresponding series. To evaluate this quality criterion, there is a fundamental need for accessibility to machine readable metadata. These aspects as well as the other issues mentioned in Table 1 follow existing principles such as FAIR or 5-star data [5]. Overcoming these issues is crucial for providing any (semi-)automated service. Here, we present the required background and the existing related works.

2.1 Event, Event Series and Proceedings as Core Entities

A common way of referencing scientific events is by linking to the proceedings of the event. In doing so, the events and event series are handled as second class citizens. As Marcel Ackermann from dblp states “Events != Proceedings . . . with plenty of crazy examples for crazy situations” [2]. Figure 1 shows the core entities and relations that are relevant for a scientific event corpus. Event, Event Series and Proceedings are highlighted in blue as these entities are in the focus of a scientific event corpus. All relations are 1:n relations – for example, multiple proceedings volumes for a single event or multiple events per proceedings volume are common. These 1:n relations are an obstacle to uniquely identifying an event if there are no PID, which might be used as foreign keys. Unfortunately, the persistent identifiers such as DOI, ISBN, ORCID and ROR are not available in the metadata as consistently as needed for disambiguation and event series completion.

Fig. 1. Dependency of Core Entities in Scientific Event Knowledge Graph

2.2 Persistent Identifiers for Events

For the unique identification and linking/referencing of entities of the types Paper, Scholar and Proceedings, there are already adopted persistent identifiers such as Digital Object Identifier (DOI) [31] and Open Researcher and Contributor ID (ORCID) [43,4]. For the type Organization, the Research Organization Registry (ROR) [53,37] is getting popular. For scientific events, the idea of using persistent identifiers as linking elements has been proposed [3,6,20] and a first conference PID has been minted in 2021 [19]. A main obstacle for introducing such PIDs is the frequent shifting of responsibility for event organization which makes it hard to add this to the workflow for organizing events. The best potential approach currently seems to make conference PID minting a feature of event organization software or other already automated parts of the event life cycle.

A conference reference is used to uniquely identify a conference [18] from which an **event signature** can be derived. The event signature consists of identifying metadata of the event. As long as PID for conferences are not widely available, the reference

often consists of an “Acronym Year” combination such as “TPDL 2020”. We will dissect the following citation reference which points to the proceedings of the TPDL 2020:

Proceedings of the 24th International Conference
on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries,
TPDL 2020, Lyon, France, August 25-27, 2020

The following elements commonly used in references may be extracted from such a reference and be used as an event signature. These may be supplied as computer readable metadata or obtained by natural language processing, such as parsing the event reference.

Acronym: a short name for the conference often consisting of 3 to 8 upper case letters trying to be unique but actually often being ambiguous. For instance, TPDL may refer to the International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries.

Frequency: annual, biannual, triennial – most events have an annual frequency and this is mostly not stated explicitly.

Event scope: target location-specific scope of the conference such as “International”, “European”, “East Asian”

Event type: Conference, Workshop, Symposium, etc.

Year: a two or four digit reference to the year in which the event took place (2020)

Ordinal: often used to enumerate the conference series instances (24th)

Date: start date and sometimes end date or date range of the conference – may appear in different formats (August 25-27)

Location: description of the location of the conference often consisting of country, region and city – sometimes with details about the exact venue (Lyon, France)

Title: the title often contains scope, type and subject of the conference (... on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries)

Organization: the organization responsible for the conference – often abbreviated such as ACM, IEEE, MIT

Subject: description and the scientific scope on what the conference is about, often prefixed with “on” (Digital Libraries)

Delimiters: a variety of syntactic delimiters such as blanks, comma, colon, brackets are used depending on the citation style.

The information content of a typical event signature is higher than necessary for identification purposes which is helpful for entity matching and disambiguation, error correction and identification of predatory events which often try to imitate reputable conferences.

2.3 Bidirectional Traceability

The need for bidirectional traceability of artefacts is relevant on two levels in the context of the conceptual scientific knowledge graph. From a requirements management point of view it should be possible to trace from user needs and concepts based on these needs via design elements such as ontologies and data source schemata to implementation artefacts such as actual data source content [24]. On the implementation and reification level, recommender systems, quality checks and other use cases depend on the bidirectional traceability between the core entities that are in the focus of this work, as discussed further in Section 2.1.

2.4 Related Work

Existing Corpora of Scientific Events. A list of more than 100 potential platforms and sources has been collected by the ConfIDent [10] project team [11] and prioritized according to the project goals. Table 2 shows a selection of this list that includes the platforms used as data sources for this work as of April 2022.

Table 2. Summary of characteristics for the selected platforms covering scientific event metadata

Corpora	Earliest Ev.	Latest Ev.	#Ev.	#Ev.Series	TPDL Link	Format	Access
dblp	1951	2022	50248	5308	ercimdl	XML	Download
Crossref	1948	2022	55441	--		JSON	RESTful API
ConfRef	1951	2018	37945	4857	tpdl	JSON	RESTful API
CEUR-WS	1994	2022	3133	--		HTML	Scraping
GND	1838	2022	742935	122825	1092455191	RDF	Download
OpenResearch	1986	2022	9520	1065	TPDL	Semantic MediaWiki	API
WikiCFP	2007	2022	90068	6019	2869	HTML	Scraping
Wikidata	1981	2022	7552	4232	Q5412433	RDF	SPARQL query
TIBKAT	1892	2022	765726	--		XML	Download

The **dblp** (Digital Bibliography and Library Project) platform [55,38] is a bibliographic database covering major metadata of papers, authors and scientific events from the computer science domain. Another such platform is **Crossref** [50,27] that is mainly a digital object identifier (DOI) registration agency that provides bulk public access to metadata via Web APIs. The other platform that seems to have overlapping data from dblp and Crossref is **ConfRef** [12,20]. It provides conference metadata of 5 computer science domain via a search dialog that includes keyword, location and time. However, ConfRef has not been updated since 2019. Another important source of metadata for this work was **CEUR-WS** [8,34] which is a free open access platform for publishing workshop Proceedings. That is one of our intended showcases for event series completion and making the metadata available in semantic form [35,54]. The **GND** file that stands for Gemeinsame Normdatei (translated as Integrated Authority) [23,26] is an international authority file curated by the German National Library (DNB). **OpenResearch** [44,63] is a mostly crowd curated wiki of scientific entities, which mainly focuses on events. It covers metadata of ~ 10000 events from ~ 1000 event series. One known source for searching upcoming events of computer science is **WikiCFP** [67,30] that mainly includes calls for papers (CfP) of scientific events. Despite calling itself a wiki for CfPs, it does not provide any wiki-based curation possibility, but mostly connects events series to dblp pages. The **Wikidata** [70,66] knowledge graph is an additional metadata source for the scholarly domain in general, as it includes factual data for the international Wikipedia encyclopedias. The library catalog **TIBKAT** of Technische Informationsbibliothek Hannover [61] supplies a subset of GND that has more detailed data for the proceedings in the focus of this library.

Existing Databases of Scientific Events. Here, we also list the top academic search databases that are also used as search engines for scholarly artefacts. These are potential targets for linking and providing provenance meta data. The numbers present the number of entries in each of these databases as of May 2022. The list contains the top five commonly used databases from our point of view ⁷:

⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_academic_databases_and_search_engines

1. Google Scholar [25,39] (389 Mn)
2. AMiner [60] (265 Mn)
3. Bielefeld Academic Search Engine (BASE) [49] (260 Mn)
4. The Lens [7,46] (228 Mn)
5. OpenAlex [45] (205 Mn)

Accessing metadata of these databases does not follow FAIR principles. A note about OpenAlex [45] is that it is the successor project of the Microsoft Academic Knowledge Graph (MAKG) presented by Färber [21], which has been discontinued in 2021. It contained 15704 conference instances for 4337 conference series.

Existing Metadata Schema and Ontology for Conferences. Several metadata schemas and ontologies specifically designed for scientific artefacts have been proposed. A comprehensive overview of these works is provided by Vahdati [62]. Table 3 summarizes existing ontologies for scientific events that we checked for alignment with and reuse for our intended future integration platforms ConfIDent and Wikidata.

Table 3. Aspects of ontologies covering scientific events

Ontology Title	Since	Scope
Semantic Web Research Community (SWRC [59])	2005	Paper, Event , Organization, Topic, Project
The Event Ontology [51]	2007	Agent, Event, Factors, Place, Product, Time
Scholarly Event Description (SEDE [33] ABC [36])	2009	Act, Agent, Event , Relation, Resource, Role
Bibliographic Ontology Specification (BiBO [22])	2009	Agent, Document, Event
the Citation Typing Ontology (CiTO [48])	2011	Citation, Paper
FRBR-aligned Bibliographic Ontology (FaBiO [48])	2012	Agent, Expression, Item, Manifestation, Work
GND Ontology [26]	2012	Event , Eventseries , Place, Work
The Conference Ontology [41]	2016	Agent, Document, OrganisedEvent , Site
Semantic Publishing and Reference (SPAR [47])	2018	see Fabio
Scientific Events Ontology (OR-SEO [17])	2018	Event , Event Series
Wikidata [69](Scholia) [40]	2018	Paper, Conf. Series , Academic Conference
The Academic Event Ontology (AEON [58])	2020	AcademicEvent , AcademicEventSeries

3 The ConferenceCorpus

As shown in Figure 2 we adapted the steps of the METaDATA Life (MEDAL) cycle proposed by Vahdati [62] to create the ConferenceCorpus. In our experience, the cycle steps are actually interconnected, forming a network rather than a cycle. The rest of the section includes description of the steps.

Selection A list of 100 potential platforms and sources has been collected by the ConfIDent [10] project team⁸ and prioritized according to the project goals.

Extraction Depending on the format and access provided by the different data-sources as shown in table 2 the extraction

Fig. 2. Steps of Metadata Life Cycle

⁸ https://rq.bitplan.com/index.php/List_of_Platforms

was performed. **Transformation** The metadata was transformed to native Python data types as List of Dicts⁹ and stored in an SQLite relational database. To prepare the interlinking, a common set of properties was empirically identified by matching the needed event signature properties with the properties available in the data sources. Some properties such as city, region, country and ordinal had to be extracted by enrichment steps as outlined below. An SQL view was then created that allows to query over all records. <https://wiki.bitplan.com/index.php/ConferenceCorpus#Event> shows the resulting database schema. Figure 3 shows the common event properties. **Interlinking** Direct Interlinking of Events and Eventseries is possible via common key/foreign-key relations, which are, e.g., available between WikiCFP and dblp. Identifiers such as ISBN and DOI are partly available. **Enrichment** To improve the interlinking of items, the Proceedings Title Parser (cf. Section 3.1) and Named Entity Recognition for locations (cf. Section 3.1) have been applied. **Curation** The curation process of the different data sources was not under the control of this work for most data sources. Only for OpenResearch and Wikidata there was the possibility to directly modify the data. **Mining** For mining of scientific event series from multiple data sources we used a semi-automated approach. Using the ConferenceCorpus REST API, we queried the metadata and exported it to a spreadsheet, in which the rows are sorted by year and ordinal. Duplicates were manually detected and removed and rows of columns from different sources collected via formulas for export to the target databases such as OpenResearch and Wikidata. **Quality Assessment** Quality Assessment applies to the entities themselves and not the metadata. One quality indicator of an academic event series is how established a series is. See Section 4.2 for the ordinal distribution analysis. **Analysis** Analysis of the data is possible via queries over the SQL views “event” and “eventseries” based on the common properties as, e.g., shown in the UML [42] class diagram Figure 3, as well as “federated queries” that collect results from different sources, and by performing extraction steps such as NLP. **Visualization** Results were visualized using Python tools such as Matplotlib [29] and SciPy [65].

3.1 The ConferenceCorpus Platform

The ConferenceCorpus is combination of a dataset, web a portal and open source Python library which was created as a part of ConfIDent project [10,13].¹⁰ The goal of the ConferenceCorpus is to enable federated queries over different scientific event metadata sources that will support event series completion. Two main components of the platform are described here:

Conference Reference Parser. Since the metadata for scientific events is currently often only available as natural language references, an extraction mechanism is needed to supply the event signature elements in a digital, computer readable format. As a first step, a Proceedings Title Parser (PTP [15]) is implemented with the intent to complete missing metadata from references such as proceedings titles or scientific event citations. PTP allows to enter a reference e.g., TPDL 2020 (shown in section 2.2) interactively or via a REST API [14]. PTP creates a computer readable event signature and searches for fitting event references in the data sources of the ConferenceCorpus.

Location NLP. It is noteworthy that some of the extracted information such location remains ambiguous especially if incomplete e.g., “Cambridge” in this proceedings:

⁹ using the pyLoDStorage [16] library we created for this purpose

¹⁰ The corpus is available at <https://github.com/WolfgangFahl/ConferenceCorpus>

Fig. 3. UML Class Diagram of Common and specific Properties of Event Entity

Proceedings of the First Annual Workshop
on Computational Learning Theory,
COLT '88, Cambridge, MA, USA,
August 3-5, 1988. ACM/MIT 1988

ConferenceCorpus employs geograpy3 [52] and nominatim [28] libraries to process natural language descriptions such as “Cambridge, MA, USA”. In this way, it finds the corresponding Wikidata items for city, region and country. In addition, a heuristic method was implemented with a lookup table to handle more ambiguous cases.

4 Results and Discussion

To showcase the effect of ConferenceCorpus, we studied three major aspects extensively: 1) event signature availability, 2) event series completeness and 3) ordinal distribution. The evaluations have been conducted on the nine data sources that had links between event and series.¹¹

4.1 Event Signature Availability

We evaluated the availability of event metadata for several platforms. Figure 4 shows the combined availability histogram of the event signature elements acronym, year, city, country, ordinal, title and start date for the data sources, and the availability histogram of the “ordinal” event signature element, which directly influences the potential for event series completion. Since the combined availability score is the product of the individual scores, a single zero value will lead to a combined zero. The main reason for the overall low results is the missing computer readability of the individual signature elements, which will be considered unavailable if the enrichment step fails.

4.2 Ordinal Distribution

Figure 5 shows three examples for ordinal frequency distributions. The Crossref distribution passes the test for being a zipfian/power law distribution and

¹¹ Further details of the results are available at <https://wiki.bitplan.com/index.php/ConferenceCorpus/statistics>.

shows the typical long tail, which was also clearly identifiable for the sources dblp, TIBKAT, WikiCFP and GND. For CEUR-WS, OpenResearch and Wikidata, the distribution was not clearly zipfian. Some aspects of these sources might explain this difference, since the choices for inclusion made by the non-zipfian distributed data sources are not as statistically random as for the zipfian ones. In the case of OpenResearch, data and software quality issues might also explain the difference.

4.3 Eventseries Completeness

For the analysis of the completeness of an event series we assume that the highest available ordinal represents the length of the series. The completeness of a series S of events e is then defined as

$$\text{completeness}(S) = \frac{|\text{ord}(S)|}{\max(\text{ord}(S))}, \text{ with } \text{ord}(S) := \{\text{ordinal}(e) \mid e \in S\}$$

Figure 6 shows the event series completeness histogram of the data sources dblp, OpenResearch, WikiCFP and Wikidata as completeness on the x-axis versus frequency of events in a decile on the y-axis. The red dashed vertical bar denotes the median completeness, e.g., 50% of the dblp events having a completeness of more than 0.6. dblp has the highest such rating of the data sources analyzed. All shown sources have frequency distributions between 5.5% and 43% of the series in the first 0–0.1 completeness decile, 0 to 29% in the 0.1 to 0.9 deciles and 6% to 26.7% in the 0.9–1.0 decile. From the resulting difference of distributions we derive the following hypotheses, which call for further analysis: The event import style of the data source influences the completeness. While OpenResearch, WikiCFP and Wikidata are crowd sourced platforms where import decisions are traditionally made individually by humans manually and therefore are naturally biased, dblp and libraries are supplied by publishers in a more systematic/unbiased way. There are limits to the achievable event series completeness when taking the classic library/indexing approach where only copies of proceedings are taken into account that are actually in the archive and even obvious gaps in the documentation of an event series will therefore not be filled.

5 Conclusion and Future Work

Bidirectional traceability in the conceptual scientific knowledge graph from any Paper, Scholar, Proceeding, Event or Event Series to any other core entity is the key

Fig. 4. Datasource Signature Completeness

Fig. 5. Histograms of ordinal distributions for the Crossref, OpenResearch, and Wikidata data sources

Fig. 6. Event Series Completeness Histograms

need that calls for event series completion as a prerequisite of a gold standard scientific event corpus. While the current state of the ConferenceCorpus already allows for semi-automatic human-in-the-loop scientific event series completion, further research is needed to improve the automation of this process. Mitigation of the data quality issues listed in Table 1 is part of what needs to be achieved. In the following, we summarize the steps necessary for that:

Metadata Curation. When curating the metadata of scientific events, the completion of the existing event series needs to be in the focus. If the 6th event is upcoming and we know of a 2nd and 3rd but no other event there must have been a 1st, 4th and 5th event.

If need be, the missing events should be curated as placeholders¹² and the series and all events should get persistent identifiers assigned to allow for completion of further details from other sources.

Metadata Extraction. For historic events the metadata can be extracted from the proceedings. This does not have to be a manual process, e.g., using optical character recognition is an option. Further information could be extracted from the original announcement and call for paper web pages (taken from the Internet Archive if not online anymore).

Metadata Errors. To mitigate errors in the metadata, a voting approach from different sources should be applied. Making sure that multiple sources agree on the metadata is also a means for spam prevention.

Metadata Readability. For future events the computer readability of metadata is best achieved by integration with the infrastructure/software that is used during the lifecycle of a scientific event. The event signature elements should be made available in digital form, e.g., the ordinal number one should be available as the integer value 1 instead of the natural language “First, 1st, 1.” as part of the title.

Predatory Event Detection Whether an event is considered as predatory is not a binary decision – there is a scale between “highly reputed” and “fully predatory” that is subjective and cause for legal debates. Rating systems as being in use in commercial portals for goods and services are not applicable in this context since scientific quality is not to be confused with popularity. Still predatory scientific events might be identified by their need to try to mimic reputed events with slight differences to be identified. Making sure there is no “cuckoo’s egg” in an event series is the goal here.

Future Work. In our opinion, this is just a start for a bigger picture we have in supporting services driven by scientific event metadata. The next immediate future steps which we intend to pursue are listed here:

Time Complexity of Platform The current approach for selecting, extracting, interlinking, enriching and curation is leading to update cycles of a few weeks to a few months. This is too slow for being a timely and reliable source for, e.g., recommender systems. The currently chosen technology stack limits the interoperability options to a REST API and direct access to the underlying relational database which is available for download.

Event Corpus Gestalt The current gestalt of scientific event corpora is suboptimal for the task. A better choice of architectural styles and technology stacks that have a proper separation of concerns for user frontend (Curation, Query, Dashboard), persistency backend and domain specific handling of the content is needed. Instead of the current static approach an event driven, observatory style based on triggers as outline below should be applied. APIs for communication with other systems should be offered and accepted instead of the currently more common query or download options.

¹² Libraries and indexes do not work with such placeholders, but platforms such as Wikidata do use such stubs.

Improving the Automation of Event Lifecycle Trigger handling During the lifecycle of a scientific event the steps: Announcement, Call for Papers, Execution. Presentation of Submissions, Publication, Indexing and later Citation all offer opportunities to gather metadata for the event in a manual, semi-automatic or even automatic way depending on the availability and accessibility of digital traces of these steps.

A promising candidate is a “drag&drop” solution that accepts scientific publication output, e.g., in PDF format and combines existing citation reference extraction with our conference reference parsing and semi-automatic spreadsheet curation.

Wikidata as the Preferred Integration Platform We imagine a gold standard event corpus to be an integration platform and not so much a database of its own. There are many commercial and non commercial offerings already available that, when integrated according to the FAIR principles, will form an excellent distributed scientific knowledge graph that may be navigated from any of the core entities as outlined in Section 2.1. The integration platform should only keep as much own data as necessary and otherwise be integrated via links and APIs. Metadata properties and data should only be included for the following reasons:

- to offer a target for linking and providing provenance metadata,
- to supply identification and disambiguation information, e.g., as part of the event signature,
- to improve access speed by caching more details (which should be refreshed often enough to be up to date and only used when access to the original is not available or not fast enough).

We believe that Wikidata [70] has the potential to be such an integration platform. The platform is provided by the independent non commercial Wikimedia Foundation. The community behind Wikidata provides services such as Scholia [56] (which provides visual profiles for entities relevant in this context) and organizes projects such as WikiCite [68] and Wikidata:Project Events [69]. The WikiCite community drives the scientific content in Wikidata [70]. Simon Cobb’s [9] import of 4,500 scientific event series entries from dblp to Wikidata in 2021 is most notable step which we intend to extend by also providing the event series completion for these series.

Scientific Event and Event Series metadata Curation improvements The data quality issues shown in Table 1 are related to metadata curation for events and series. Most curation institutions tend to favor manual curation over automated curation, assuming the quality of the content is increased this way. When entering a new metadata record, the whole series needs to be taken into account – the effort for completion and conversion to computer readability and other data quality improvements is therefore much higher than for the single new event. Combining advantages of human curation with automated and semi-automated/human in the loop curation tools will improve quality and speed. Allowing spreadsheet-style editing with the enhancement and validation steps embedded into the tool is a good candidate. Existing tools such as OpenRefine are not fit to fulfill this role yet since they are targeted to data scientists and developers and not curators or others willing to participate in curation.

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